

Electrical conductivity of *s*-acetylthiocholine halides and perchlorate in acetonitrile at 35 °C

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Abstract : The conductance of *s*-acetylthiocholine halides and perchlorate has been measured in acetonitrile at 35 °C. The data were analyzed using the Fuoss-Onsager equation for 1 : 1 associated electrolytes. Λ_0 (equivalent conductance at infinite dilution), a^0 (contact distance of approach) and K_A (association constant) were computed. K_A values were analyzed on the basis of the solvent separated-ion pair model. The electrostatic Stokes' radii ($R^+ + R^-$) were calculated and their sum was compared with the value of a^0 favoring the above model.

Keywords : Conductivity, *s*-acetylthiocholine salts, acetonitrile, ionic association.

Introduction

The nature of solute species in acetonitrile is of interest due to increasing use of acetonitrile as a reaction medium¹. Conductance measurements for some 1 : 1 electrolyte *s*-acetylthiocholine salts were made to study ion-association in acetonitrile.

Results and discussion

An approximate value of Λ_0 estimated from the extrapolation of Λ vs $C^{1/2}$ plot using the data in Table 1 was employed in Fuoss-Kraus-Shedlovsky (F.K.S.) equation

to obtain accurate values of Λ_0 ,

$$\frac{1}{\Lambda S_{(z)}} = \frac{1}{\Lambda_0} + \frac{(C\Lambda S_{(z)} f^2)}{K_D \Lambda_0^2}, \quad (1)$$

where K_D is the dissociation constant, f is an activity coefficient and $S_{(z)}$ is the Shedlovsky's function as tabulated by Daggett for different values of z . The value of z being obtained using equation,

$$z = \alpha (C\Lambda)^2 / \Lambda_0^{3/2} \quad (2)$$

α is the limiting tangent (Onsager slope). The plot of $1/\Lambda$

Table 1. Conductance of *s*-acetylthiocholine salts in acetonitrile at 35 °C

Acetylthiocholine bromide		Acetylthiocholine iodide		Acetylthiocholine perchlorate	
$10^4 C^a$	Λ^b	$10^4 C$	Λ	$10^4 C$	Λ
14.2129	184.30	7.1824	174.58	2.0164	183.11
12.2500	187.30	6.2001	178.76	1.5376	189.71
10.0758	189.70	5.4756	181.64	1.2769	193.54
9.6100	191.80	4.9284	184.57	1.0816	196.97
8.7025	193.20	4.4521	186.84	0.9216	199.85
7.9524	194.60	4.0804	188.52	0.7921	202.86
7.2900	195.80	3.8025	189.67	0.7225	204.12
6.7600	196.90	3.4969	191.57		

^aequiv L⁻¹, ^b Ω^{-1} , equiv cm².

$S_{(z)}$ vs $(\Lambda_0 S_{(z)} f^2)$ gives $1/\Lambda_0$ as the intercept and $1/K_D \Lambda_0^2$ as the slope. More accurate values of Λ_0 , $J(a)$ and K_A were derived using Fuoss-Onsager eq. (2) and starting by the value Λ_0 which obtained from (F.K.S.) equation. The accuracies required in these computation are ± 0.02 for Λ_0 ; ± 2 for $J < 200$, ± 5 for $J = (200 \rightarrow 1000)$ and ± 10 for $J > 1000$. Fig. 1 shows the variation of a° with J by the aid of this calibration curve, where J is a function of a° represented by the following eq. (2),

$$J = \sigma_1 \Lambda_0 + \sigma_2 \quad (3)$$

where σ_1 and σ_2 are the function of J . The derived constants are represented in Table 2. Λ_0 increased from *s*-acetylthiocholine bromide to perchlorate with increases

in ionic equivalent conductance of the anions. The values of a° decreased with increasing the size of anions indicating that it has its effect on the extent of ion pairing. The solvation of these anions increased in the order : $\text{Br}^- > \text{I}^- > \text{ClO}_4^-$, which agreed with the trend of a° . From the electrostatic point of view, as the distance between the cation and the anion increases in the order : $\text{Br}^- > \text{I}^- > \text{ClO}_4^-$, the force of attraction decreases in the order : $\text{ClO}_4^- > \text{I}^- > \text{Br}^-$. In our case the trend indicated that K_A increased with decreasing the size of anions.

El-Hamamy *et al.*^{3,4} found that, for *s*-acetylthiocholine halides and perchlorate, the order of solvation (a°) in acetonitrile at 25 °C and 30 °C was $\text{Br}^- > \text{I}^- >$

Fig. 1. Variation of J and a° in acetonitrile at 35 °C.

Table 2. Characteristic parameters for *s*-acetylthiocholine salts in acetonitrile at 35 °C

Salts	Λ_0 ($\Omega^{-1} \text{equiv}^{-1} \text{cm}^2$)	J	K_A	a° (Å)	σ_A
Ac.Th.Br	218.72	3267.2	109.0	6.00	0.126
Ac.Th.I	220.84	3037.3	409.13	5.86	0.268
Ac.Th.ClO ₄	223.29	3092.4	1228.4	5.37	0.267

ClO_4^- , i.e. solvation (a°) decreased with increasing the size of anions, in agreement with present results. Conductance measurements studies of *s*-acetylthiocholine halides and perchlorate in methanol⁵, ethanol⁶, *n*-propanol⁷, *n*-butanol⁸ and 2-propanol⁹ at 25 °C. They were reported to follow the order of solvation (a°) of $\text{Br}^- > \text{I}^- > \text{ClO}_4^-$, which agree with present results. The gradual

decrease of a° with K_A among the salts was attributed to the relative position of the anion with respect to the cation which may not be completely spherical. The increase of K_A with increasing the size of anions of *s*-acetylthiocholine halides and perchlorate could be explained in the terms of the U term in eq. (4)¹⁰,

$$\ln K_A = \ln(4\pi N a^{\circ 3}/3000) + (e^2/a^{\circ} D k T) + U \quad (4)$$

where, $U = \Delta S/k - E_s/kT$; $\Delta S/k$ is the entropy factor which illustrates the probability of the orientation of solvent molecules around the ions, and E_s/kT is an energy factor describing the energy of the solvent molecules with respect to both free ions and ion-pair. The values of U term of *s*-acetylthiocholine halides and perchlorate are given in Table 3. The results revealed that the value of U slightly increased from Br^- to ClO_4^- whereas the trend in a° is $\text{Br}^- < \text{I}^- < \text{ClO}_4^-$, showing that entropy term predominant over the ion-dipole interaction term. Therefore, the solvent separated ion-pair model can be applied¹¹. In this model a multiple-step association is suggested in the Scheme 1.

where X = number of escaping solvent molecules from solvation.

Scheme 1

Table 3. Calculated values of K_2 and U of *s*-acetylthiocholine halides and perchlorate in acetonitrile at 35 °C

Salts	K_A	K_1	K_2	U
Ac.Th.Br	109.00	6.729	15.199	2.78
Ac.Th.I	409.13	6.658	60.452	4.12
Ac.Th.ClO ₄	1228.4	6.479	188.59	5.24

Table 4. Calculation of the radii of the ions for *s*-acetylthiocholine salts in acetonitrile at 35 °C

Salts	Λ_0^a	$\lambda_0^- \eta_0^b$	λ_0^{-a}	λ_0^{+a}	Av. λ_0^{+a}	R^+ (Å)	R^- (Å)	$R^+ + R^-$	a° (Å)
Ac.Th.Br	218.72	0.33697	107.59	111.13			2.432	4.810	6.00
Ac.Th.I	220.84	0.34887	111.39	109.45	109.85 ± 0.85	2.379	2.349	4.728	5.86
Ac.Th.ClO ₄	223.29	0.35802	114.31	108.98			2.289	4.668	5.37

^a $\Omega^{-1} \text{equiv}^{-1} \text{cm}^2$, ^b $\Omega^{-1} \text{equiv}^{-1} \text{cm}^2$.

The association constant is given by the following expression (eq. 5),

$$\begin{aligned}
 K_A &= K \Sigma = \frac{[C_{(\text{ion-pairs})}]}{[C_{(s\text{-Acetylthiocholine})^+}] [C_{X^-(\text{Solvent})_n}]} \\
 &= K_1 (1 + K_2) \quad (5)
 \end{aligned}$$

where, $K_A = K \Sigma$ is obtained from the conductance measurements

$$K_1 = \frac{4\pi N a^{\circ 3}}{3000} e^b \quad (6)$$

K_2 was thus calculated. The results compiled in Table 3, indicated that K_2 increased from Br^- to ClO_4^- , i.e. the ion-pair preferred the desolvated form (case II) than the solvated form (case I).

Radii of ions :

The electrostatic radii R^+ and R^- are given by eq. (7) :

$$R^{\pm} = 0.8194 \times 10^{-8} / \lambda_0^{\pm} \eta_0 \quad (7)$$

In the present case λ_0^- values were obtained from the intercept of the straight lines resulting from the plots of Walden products $\Lambda_0 \eta_0$ versus the reciprocal of the molecular weight as previously discussed¹². To calculate λ_0^+ for *s*-acetylthiocholine⁺, the average value obtained for λ_0^+ in case of the Br^- , I^- and ClO_4^- was used in calculations. Applying Stokes' equation, one may obtain the values of both R^+ and R^- . These data are recorded in Table 4. It can be seen from Table 4 that the values of a° are greater than the electrostatic radii ($R^+ + R^-$) which obtained from Stokes' equation. The greater a° values are probably attributed to ion solvation.

Experimental

Electrolytes and acetonitrile were purified as described^{13,14}. Specific conductance for acetonitrile at 35 °C was found to be $(4-7 \times 10^{-8}) \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$. The density of acetonitrile was found to be 0.7652 g/cm^3 at 35 °C. Its

viscosity coefficient measured at 35 °C was found 0.31309×10^{-2} poise. The value of dielectric constant for acetonitrile used was 35.36¹⁵. Dilution was carried out successively into the cell by siphoning the solvent by means of weighing pipette.

Crison Cl P31 Conductivity meter was used. The cell is fitted with bright platinum electrodes, with constant 0.1 cm^{-1} .

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